

NIGHT SKY

TOURISM:

A QUICK

START GUIDE

FOR INHABITANTS OF RURAL AREAS

Night sky tourism is any tourism activity that happens **outdoors at night**. This guide is designed to help you come up with an interesting and locally relevant night sky activity that will attract guests to your area and stimulate the local economy.

INTERNATIONAL ASTRONOMICAL UNION | OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

For more resources and support, visit www.astrotourism.astro4dev.org or email astrotourism@astro4dev.org

1. CHOOSING A NIGHTTIME ACTIVITY

Pick **ONE** idea from these, or use them as inspiration to come up with your own idea for an experience at night. This idea will form the core of the experience.

When you're choosing this idea, keep in mind what is available to you and the location you plan to offer this activity in. Choose something that you already have the skills and resources for.

LOCAL FOOD

A traditional meal under the stars

Teaching people how to prepare food over fire

Food tasting of local items in the dark (wine, honey, fruits, etc.)

Nighttime picnic

TIP: Try to find an activity that would also work indoors or in a sheltered setting in case of bad weather.

CULTURAL PERFORMANCES

Singing or music performances in the dark

Traditional dances by a fire

Cultural storytelling under the stars

Darkness sound therapy

Yoga under the stars

Guided meditation in the dark

WELLNESS & MINDFULNESS

ART

Painting by the fire

Dyeing textiles by a fire

Making local crafts by a fire

NIGHTTIME WALKS

Nighttime village walking tours

Wildlife walks: listening for the sounds of different animals

2. HOW CAN YOU USE LOCALLY MADE CRAFTS AND OBJECTS IN YOUR ACTIVITY?

Try to incorporate as many local crafts and cultural objects into your experience as you can. These cultural touchpoints will add authenticity to your experience. They can also be sold to guests at the end of the experience (make sure you sell them new items, not the ones they have used). Consider the following examples, or any other local crafts and objects that you can think of that can be used in your experience.

POTTERY

Plates

Bowls

Cups and mugs

BASKETRY

Baskets

Bags

Woven mats

TEXTILES

Scarves and shawls

Blankets

Carpets

Napkins

Clothing items

BEADWORK

Using beads to accessorise other items

Jewellery

TIP: Use as many different cultural crafts and objects that you can think of in your chosen activity.

example: for a 'dinner under the stars' experience, use plates, mugs and bowls made by a local potter, napkins with local prints, and provide locally woven shawls for people to keep warm while eating outdoors.

3. CULTURAL ASTRONOMY

Every culture in history has developed a unique relationship with objects in the night sky. Here are some aspects of your own cultural astronomy to research and include in your night sky experience. You might know some of these stories yourself, or you can reach out to family and community members or cultural experts to find out more. You can also reach out to your country's [IAU National Outreach Coordinator](#) to ask for help with finding this information.

THE SUN AND MOON

The Sun and Moon sometimes represent Gods or deities, or are believed to influence human and animal behaviour. Here are some cultural perspectives of the Sun and Moon that you can look into.

The surface
of the Moon

Phases of
the Moon

Lunar
calendars

STARS AND CONSTELLATIONS

Stars and constellations are often used for orientation, navigation and timekeeping. They may also be believed to be linked to personal and community fortunes. Here are some cultural perspectives of stars and constellations that you can look into.

Navigation and
finding directions

Farming and
agriculture

Timing rituals,
festivals, holy
months, or
other events

Astrology

Star/sidereal
calendars

SPECIAL EVENTS

Some special events can be culturally interpreted as good or bad omens, or have certain rituals or beliefs surrounding them.

Meteor showers

Eclipses

TIP: Find perspectives of the night sky that are unique to your culture. This will make your night sky experience unique and attractive to visitors.

4. THE LOGISTICS OF THE ACTIVITY

LOCATION

Here are some important things to keep in mind when you are choosing where to carry out your activity:

Make sure your locations are safe from people and wild animals

Obtain proper permission to use the locations from the people who own them

Choose a back-up indoor location in case of bad weather

Make sure people have access to bathrooms before or during the experience

Make sure you obtain the proper licenses and approvals for your activities

ACCESSIBILITY

These are questions that will help clarify guests' expectations of the activity, and make sure they are prepared.

What can you do to accommodate people with disabilities?

Will you provide food and beverages during the activity?

Is the activity pet-friendly?

Is the activity child-friendly?

Will you provide any special clothing or equipment needed, or do they bring it?

Will you provide transportation to/from the activity?

BEFORE THE EXPERIENCE

Make sure you let guests know what to expect, and prepare for emergency situations.

First Aid Kit

A plan for what to do in case of emergencies (e.g. someone falling sick during the experience)

Brief guests about what to expect and what to bring with them

Find similar activities to yours that happen during the day, and try to keep your price close to this

Make a list of all the costs of your activity, and find a price that allows you to make a profit

PRICING

Set a profitable and affordable price.

5. TEST RUN

Test out your activity from start to finish on friends and family. Ask them for feedback and note down what they say can be improved. Did everything go according to plan, or were there things you hadn't thought of? Make a note to accommodate these.

6. EXTRA TIPS

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Responsible nighttime tourism involves protecting the environment that the experience happens in. Following these tips should help you prevent environmental damage.

Do not litter or leave trash at the activity location

Limit the number of people who can participate to avoid excessive damage to the environment

Do not make unnecessary noise

Limit or completely avoid using single-use plastic items

PROTECTING THE NIGHT SKY

Since night sky tourism is greatly enhanced by a good view of the moon and stars, using light responsibly and in low amounts helps to maximise the number of stars visible. Responsible lighting also reduces health impacts on people and nocturnal animals. Here are some guidelines for using lighting during your experience.

Turn off as many outdoor lights as possible

Try to limit your use of artificial light to candles and firelight

Where electric light is needed, use red light instead of white/yellow

Shield outdoor lights to reduce glare

TIP: For more responsible lighting guidelines, you can refer to [DarkSky's Five Principles for Responsible Outdoor Lighting](#).

7. SPREADING THE WORD

MARKETING & PROMOTION

Marketing is key to reaching a wider audience and ensuring your night sky experience gets the attention it deserves.

TIP: Get some high quality images of your experience as it's happening, and use these to market the experience. Hire a professional photographer if you have the budget for it.

Use social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and X/Twitter to showcase your experience

Set up a booth at local community events to distribute flyers and engage with potential participants

Reach out to local newspapers, magazines, and influential bloggers for coverage

Develop a simple website or blog to provide detailed information about your night sky experience

Build an email list of interested participants and send regular updates about upcoming events, special promotions, or exclusive offers

Encourage participants to share their experiences with friends and family. Consider implementing a referral program

Partner with local businesses, such as restaurants, cafes, or hotels to cross-promote your experience. Offer package deals or discounts to their customers

Reach out to local and regional tourism agencies to include your experience in their promotional materials

PLATFORMS TO SHOWCASE YOUR EXPERIENCE

AirBnB Experiences

Viator

EventBrite

Facebook Events

Travel Forums & Communities

8. NEXT STEPS

If you would like to develop this idea further and work towards developing a business plan, please refer to our resource **Night Sky Tourism for Communities around Observatories**. While that resource is targeted at observatories, communities around observatories, and support organisations, you can make use of the Business Model Canvas idea in it to develop and clarify yours further. Section 3 of the resource contains guidelines to creating a Business Model Canvas, and a sample Business Model Canvas for experiences that you can use to develop your own.

For more resources and support, visit astro4dev.org, or email us at astrotourism@astro4dev.org.

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